

Current Positions of Postdoctoral Fellows Completing NESCent Funding

Name	Appointment	Current Employment	Starting Date
Brian O'Meara	Assistant Professor	University of Tennessee, Knoxville	August 1, 2009
Paula Spaeth	Assistant Professor	Biology and Natural Resources at Northland College	August 31, 2009
Brian Sidlauskas	Assistant Professor	Department of Fisheries and Wildlife, Oregon State University	July 1, 2009
Einat Covo-Hazkani's	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Molecular Genetics and Microbiology, Duke University	May 31, 2009
Burleigh, Gordon	Assistant Professor	Department of Botany, University of Florida at Gainesville	August 15, 2008
Fisher, Kirsten	Assistant Professor	Department of Biological Sciences, California State University at Los Angeles	September 1, 2008
Granek, Joshua	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Biology, Duke University	August 1, 2007

Hereford, Joe	NSF Minority Postdoctoral Fellow	Department of Biology, University of Maryland, College Park	January 1, 2007
Hoeksema, Jason	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Mississippi	August 1, 2007
Hopkins, Samantha	Assistant Professor	Clark Honors College, University of Oregon	September 1, 2007
Kidd, David	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Centre for Population Biology, Imperial College London, United Kingdom	September 1, 2008
Price, Samantha	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Evolution and Ecology, University of California, Davis	November 1, 2008
Zanne, Amy	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Missouri, St Louis	August 1, 2008
Zwickl, Derrick	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Kansas	May 1, 2008

Date: 7/22/2009